

MEDICAL SCIENCES

INDIVIDUAL SELECTION OF METAL ALLOYS IN THE MANUFACTURE OF DENTAL PROSTHESES FOR EACH PATIENT

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Abstract

In recent years, materials new in composition and quality have been widely used for the manufacture of dentures. The biocompatibility of the materials from which the prostheses are made for the patient is a sign of his dental and general health and ensures an appropriate quality of life .

Keywords: *metal alloys, galvanoses, dental structures, electrochemical potential, bridges.*

Relevance of the topic In the manufacture of artificial dental structures, metal alloys are widely used. The composition of the alloys includes iron, chromium, nickel, cobalt, silicon, zinc, molybdenum, manganese, gold, palladium, etc., there are about 20 of them. manganese, cadmium, copper, magnesium. During soldering, the structure of the metal changes. In the manufacture of one-piece cast dental structures, the casting structure does not always become homogeneous. A dental prosthesis inserted into the patient's oral cavity, even if it has hidden metal elements (the basis of ceramic-metal, metal-plastic structures), will be subject to an electrochemical process, since its inherent electrochemical potential will be determined [1;5]. It can be measured relative to hydrogen, the potential of which is taken as zero. Metals, according to the increase in their electrode potential, form a series of metal voltages [4]. When using metal alloys for dentures, some patients experience symptoms of intolerance.

[8]. The term intolerance itself is collective and does not contain information about the etiopathogenesis of the disease. Scientists have discovered three main types of impact of oral metal inclusions on the body: electrogalvanic, allergic and chemical-toxic [2]. But in practice it is very difficult to identify the components of this impact. In addition, they all dealt with the consequences that occurred in the oral cavity or in the patient's body in one case or another. One of the consequences of the influence of metal alloys on the patient's body is galvanosis - the occurrence of electrochemical potentials in the oral cavity. In the event of a complication, even a galvanic disease can occur if symptoms of damage to the body as a whole are added to the local ones.

As an alternative to avoiding the phenomena of galvanosis and galvanic disease, together with the achievement of a better aesthetic appearance of dentures, one-piece cast structures with a metal-ceramic or metal-plastic coating were introduced into the arsenal

of orthopedic dentists [5]. Modern alloys for their manufacture are chromium-nickel (for small and medium bridges) or cobalt chromium (for medium or large bridges) [6]. As you know, the metal base of these dentures is almost completely covered on the outside. But the inner metal part of the prosthesis can have direct contact with the tissues of the teeth. Currently, there are no systems for controlling the connection of the internal parts of the crowns of the teeth with cement to dental tissues. In addition, the edge of the crowns almost always has a metal strip that is in contact with the gum. That is, with prosthetics of teeth with fixed structures made of metal, which

have a metal base, the possibility of contact of surrounding tissues with metal in the patient's oral cavity cannot be excluded. Therefore, the formation of electrochemical potentials can lead to the manifestation of intolerance.

The purpose of the study was to prevent the phenomena of intolerance to metal inclusions in the patient's oral cavity, due to the presence of non-removable metal structures and electrochemical potentials.

Object and methods of research

The object of the study was 12 patients who applied to the clinic of orthopedic dentistry in order to manufacture aesthetic one-piece dental structures using metal-ceramic and metal-plastic.

Patients sought orthopedic care after symptoms of intolerance due to prosthetics with metal dentures. All patients had elevated electrochemical potentials (from 150 to 190 mV). Clinically, the allergic process is manifested by such symptoms as a metallic taste, dryness of the mucous membrane, burning, hyperemia, and itching in the tongue area.

We have offered an express method for metal diagnostics for selection.

Bases of the framework of dentures. Samples regarding the choice of metal for dentures are not widely made in dental clinics. It is known the definition of

electrical potentials, according to the results of which prostheses are subject to destruction. But electric potentials are measured after the fabrication and cementation of dental structures, which leads to damage to the clinic and patients. In addition, patients acquire a negative experience, which affects the further relationship of the patient's doctor. Express diagnostics is performed before prosthetics with dental structures. It consists in a skin (application) test. This does not violate the integrity of the skin or mucous membranes. To do this, on the unharmed surface of the forearm, treated with 70 ° alcohol, a square made of the investigated metal alloy with an area of 1 cm was applied, which was covered with cellophane on top and fixed with a plaster, a similar square of 4 layers of gauze soaked in saline was applied at a distance of 3-4 cm. Withstood 24-48 hours, after which the sample was evaluated, namely:

- severe hyperemia (+),
- hyperemia, edema, papules (++)
- intense hyperemia, edema, papules and vesicles (+++),
- formation of large blisters or surface necrosis (++++)

In case of a negative test, we carry out a test with another metal, in case of doubt, we additionally apply it to the oral mucosa. For it, we perform processing and sterilization of samples. We apply the prepared sample to the buccal mucosa, we ask the patient to hold it with his own hands. Now on the face we notice the location of the sample. We stand 15-20 minutes. We remove the sample from the oral cavity. We evaluate the mucosa where the sample was located and compare it with the area of the mucosa that is not subject to the action of the metal. We alternately produce samples: first with the KHS alloy, and then with the nickel-chromium alloy. We evaluate the results of the test [3]. The application of the technique allows, even at the beginning of prosthetics, to detect the reaction of the body to the metal base, in the future it helps to prevent the occurrence of negative reactions.

Research results and discussion

Using the method of express selection of metal for dental structures, we selected materials for prosthetics for all those who applied. We conducted 12 skin (application) tests. In 2 patients with diabetes mellitus, various degrees of allergy to nickel-chromium alloy were found (electrochemical potentials were within the normal range, but there were manifestations of hyperemia, edema, subjective manifestations: burning, itching, etc.); they made prostheses from alloys with CCS, the test for which was within the normal range. 4 patients underwent mucosal (intraoral) tests in order to clarify

the results of the obtained reaction, since application tests with CCS and nickel-chromium were out of the norm. After mucosal tests, patients were asked to make metal-free constructions or contact one of the dental firms that manufactures dentures based on valuable metals. For 6 patients, in whom the application tests for the CCS alloy were within the normal range, and there were allergic manifestations for the nickel alloy, prosthetics with an alloy of silver and palladium were proposed, they had defects in the teeth in the lateral areas. We followed up the patients for a year. Electrochemical potentials were measured, ranging from 60 to 80 mV. There were no repeated complaints about intolerance.

Conclusions

The method of express choice of metal for dental prosthetics avoids the occurrence of symptoms of intolerance to metal inclusions in the environment of the patient's mouth. The method is simple to perform and does not require any damage to the skin or mucous membrane of the patient and allows the dentist to choose the metal alloy individually for each.

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